

CURRENT STATE OF ECONOMIC COOPERATION OF SCO MEMBERS: ANALYSIS, CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS

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Introduction: The history of mankind is full of examples of both accord and discord. Humanity has also experienced that cooperation, at all levels, furthers development and results in peace, prosperity and security. Discord or conflict, on the other hand, creates problems and complexities, hampering development and leading even to armed clashes. It is important to note that sustainable cooperation, particularly among neighbors, is possible only if it is comprehensive, i.e. if it embraces all important dimensions of human interaction - economic, social, political and strategic - and takes into account both internal and external factors. Indeed, external factors have gradually gained added significance in the recent past.

Over the two decades since its founding, the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO), in the spirit of pragmatism and unity, has made remarkable achievements in the three pillars of security cooperation, economic cooperation, and cultural and people-to-people exchanges, “setting an example for a new type of international relations that features mutual respect, equity, justice and win-win cooperation” and becoming “a major constructive force in the Eurasian region and global affairs.”¹ As an important foundation for the SCO’s steady development, economic cooperation has been playing a crucial role in building economic ties across the region aimed at common prosperity, which continuously adds endogenous momentum to regional cooperation and becomes a model of cooperation among emerging economies.

First, the legal basis for SCO regional economic cooperation has been constantly consolidated. In September 2001, the Memorandum on Basic Goals and Directions of Regional Economic Cooperation and Launching the Trade and Investment Facilitation Process was signed as the first SCO document in this

¹ “Remarks by Chinese President Xi Jinping at 20th Meeting of SCO Council of Heads of State,” Xinhua, November 10, 2020, http://www.xinhuanet.com/english/2020-11/10/c_139506835.htm.

regard. To reinforce the legal foundation for regional economic cooperation, the SCO countries have signed a series of documents in the subsequent years including: the Program of Multilateral Trade and Economic Cooperation (2003), the Action Plan for the Implementation of the Program of Multilateral Trade and Economic Cooperation (2004), the Joint Initiative on Accelerated Multilateral Economic Cooperation to Overcome the Global Financial and Economic Crisis Impacts and Ensure Further Economic Development (2009), the SCO Mid-Term Development Strategy (2012), the SCO Development Strategy until 2025 (2015), the List of Measures for Further Development of Project Activities within the SCO for the Period 2017-2021 (2016), a new version of the Program of Multilateral Trade and Economic Cooperation (2019), and the Action Plan for 2021-2025 on the Implementation of the Program for Multilateral Trade and Economic Cooperation (2020).

Second, mechanisms for SCO inter-governmental cooperation have been continuously improved. As the most important inter-governmental cooperation mechanism under the SCO framework, the Council of Heads of Governments (Prime Ministers) is responsible for formulating the strategies and priorities for SCO multilateral cooperation, addressing the principles and urgent issues in economic cooperation, and approving the SCO's annual budget. By the end of 2020, the Council had held 19 meetings that guided in-depth development of regional economic cooperation.

First, investment across the SCO region is steadily growing. According to UN Conference on Trade and Development statistics, SCO countries have been increasingly attractive to external capital over the years. In terms of flows, total foreign direct investment in the SCO states was only US\$52.62 billion in 2001, but the figure had surged to US\$231.56 billion by 2019². In particular, China has been rapidly stepping up investment in other SCO member countries. As SCO Secretary-General Vladimir Norov indicated, China came to the rescue of the world economy twice, during the 2008-2009 global financial crisis when it launched a massive investment program, and in 2020 when it remained the world's largest overseas investor despite the declining trend in global investment due to the coronavirus pandemic³.

Among the amount, China's non-financial direct investment to Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan had reached US\$1.55 billion and US\$1.95 billion in 2019, from

² "Foreign Direct Investment: Inward and Outward Flows and Stock, Annual," UNCTAD STAT, <https://unctadstat.unctad.org/wds/TableViewer/tableView.aspx?ReportId=96740>.

³ "SCO Will Deepen Cooperation with China, Says Secretary-General Norov," The Economic Observer, November 25, 2020, <http://www.eeo.com.cn/2020/1125/438103.shtml>.

US\$20 million and US\$1 million in 2003 respectively. China is now the two countries' largest foreign investor. Besides, China has been Pakistan's largest source of foreign investment for the past nine years, Uzbekistan's second largest foreign investor, and Kazakhstan's fourth largest foreign investor.

Under the general framework of the Treaty on Long-Term Good Neighborliness, Friendship and Cooperation, and specifically guided by the Program of Multilateral Trade and Economic Cooperation, from 2001 to 2021, the SCO countries have overcome multiple difficulties and made active efforts to explore new arenas of cooperation and innovate the patterns of cooperation, thus yielding substantial results in mechanism-building, trade, investment, finance and connectivity. All this has greatly enhanced people's well-being in the countries and the overall economic performance of the whole region, while elevating the SCO's influence in the world economy.⁴

SCO has to confront many challenges before it can gain wider trust for its newly rebranded image and escape the anti-Western labelling of the organisation. One area it should start with is more efficiency in managing public communication. Important information related to the organisation and its activities is still often unavailable equally in the SCO official languages and English. Few data points, apart from the news on the meetings, are available on the official websites, and most of the quality information about the SCO proceedings remains that from the organisation's insiders. This prevents efficient communication not only with the Western colleagues, but also with the SCO countries' own academic circles and general public. Should the SCO aim to prove its nature as the organisation of "a new type", greater transparency and efficiency should be pursued.⁵

Conclusion: The findings of this paper show that over the past 20 years since the SCO establishment in June 2001, its concept of cooperation has been constantly enriched and developed. Its cooperation mechanism has been constantly enriched and improved; and its areas of cooperation have been expanded. However, following its development over time and the advancement of its cooperation practices, it also faces challenges and development difficulties on its way forward; these include the facts of: the intensification of great power game in the region, the weakness of the sense of community between its member states and the transformation of cooperation pattern faces after

⁴ SCO. 2004, June 17. Tashkent Declaration of Heads of Members States of Shanghai Cooperation Organisation. Tashkent, (www.sectsc.org).

⁵ UNODC. 2006, September 2. "Afghan opium cultivation soars 59 percent in 2006, UNODC survey shows." Official website of United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime. Kabul. (www.unodc.org/unodc/press_release_2006_09_01.html) Viewed October 27, 2006.

expansion. With regard to its prospects, the Shanghai spirit will guide its multilateral cooperation vision. Also, the SCO mechanism provides an important guarantee for multilateral cooperation ahead. The new type of international relations will serve as an important driving force for its multilateral cooperation vision. Finally, based on our results, we believe that the SCO is fully capable of exerting greater influence and delivering greater results in the years to come.

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